
Do Teachers' and Firefighters' Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Authentic Leadership Have a Relationship?

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between leaders' authentic leadership and the dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) among firefighters and teachers. A total of 289 participants were recruited from the fields of firefighting and education using a snowball sampling technique. Participants completed three surveys: a demographic questionnaire, the Organizational Citizenship Behavior Checklist (OCB-C), and the Authentic Leadership Questionnaire (ALQ). Demographic variables include age, gender, tenure, education, marital status, occupation, and ethnicity. Multiple regression analysis was conducted to analyze the data. The results revealed that self-awareness significantly predicts OCB in both dimensions: interpersonal and organizational. Furthermore, occupation emerged as a significant predictor in OCB organization dimension. These findings highlight the importance of self-awareness in leaders for fostering organizational citizenship behavior among employees in distinct professional environments.

Keywords: Authentic Leadership, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Teachers, Firefighters

Introduction

This study focuses on Authentic Leadership by Avolio and Gardner. The Authentic Leadership model focuses on four facets of Authentic Leadership: Relational Transparency, Internalized Moral Perspective, Balanced Processing, and Self-Awareness (Gardner et al., 2005; Walumbwa et al., 2008; May et al., 2003). Authentic leaders are distinguished by their moral and ethical conduct, which fosters in their followers a sense of fairness, honesty, trustworthiness, and transparency (Walumbwa et al., 2008; Gardner et al., 2005; Gardner et al., 2019; Luthans & Avolio, 2003). Developing a positive, value-based relationship with followers is a key component of authentic leadership, and it includes inclusive decision-making and alignment with common values and beliefs (Gardner et al., 2019).

Considering growing corporate unethical behavior, the need of authentic leadership has increased, highlighting the necessity for leaders who cultivate healthy relationships via self-awareness, behavioral standards, and philosophy. This leadership approach supports a culture

of development, openness, moral, and ethical conduct, and objective decision-making (Gardner et al., 2005; Walumbwa et al., 2008; Luthans & Avolio, 2003).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior is a construct that increases organizational efficiency by encouraging followers to do actions that positively impacts organizational effectiveness (Organ, 1988; Allen & Rush, 1998; Organ et al., 2005; Podsakoff & MacKenzie, 1997). The key to this concept is the appreciation of workers who voluntarily and creatively go above and beyond their obligations of duty to help their organizations succeed beyond expectations (Katz, 1964; Bozkurt & Bal, 2012; Ahmadi, 2010; Gliska-Newe & Szostek, 2018). These employees conduct beneficial acts outside of their official positions, frequently without receiving compensation (Organ, 1988; William & Anderson, 1991; Allen & Rush, 1998). Additionally, it has been noted that when companies start a variety of welfare activities for their employees, employees behave more ethically at work and have a more positive attitude toward their organization (Bozkurt & Bal, 2012; Katz, 1964).

Community service-focused occupations, like those in the public sector, frequently have a strong work ethic that affects many aspects of job performance (Lee & Olshfski, 2002). The success of an organization depends on motivated employees who make the most of their

capabilities within the company (Choochom, 2016). Employees of the public sector, such as teachers and firefighters, exhibit organizational citizenship behaviors. These behaviors include helping work colleagues with job tasks, solving issues in the community, recognizing and suggesting solutions for public service challenges, and enhancing their organizations' reputations (Shim & Faerman, 2017). Lee and Olshfski (2002) noted that workers in professions of teaching and firefighting frequently have a strong commitment to serving the public.

According to Schmidhuber and Hilgers (2018), firefighters frequently take part in extra-role behaviors that benefit their organization and society. According to Haski Leventhal and McLeigh (2009), firefighters exhibit extraordinary altruism, often fueled by a selfless attitude that is essential to their line of duty. This altruism goes beyond their professional responsibilities and includes youth mentorship, fundraising, and equipment maintenance. Such actions while beyond their job obligations are essential to organizational effectiveness and the welfare of society (Schmidhuber & Hilgers, 2018). Fire departments must cultivate and encourage authentic leadership as it promotes positive psychological attributes and an ethical work environment (López et al., 2015; Waldron & Schary, 2019).

In the education system, schools play a crucial part in educating young scholars and it is essential that educators are motivated and satisfied (Shaheen et al., 2016). Although schools have established roles and responsibilities for teachers, these frequently do not cover the range of behaviors and actions that educators may display, particularly outside of their designated obligations (Shaheen et al., 2016). These additional behaviors, referred to as Organizational Citizenship Behaviors (OCB), are essential to schools' efficient operation. Work colleagues, students, and the school all benefit from teachers' OCB, which is influenced by organizational and individual characteristics (Shaheen et al., 2016). Therefore, it is crucial for education leaders to promote the use of authentic leadership, empowering educators to thrive and improve their OCB, which is integral to the success and efficacy of educational institutions (Shapira-Lishchinsky & Tsemach, 2014).

The subsequent analysis presents two meta-analyses examining the relationship between authentic leadership and organizational citizenship behavior.

In their meta-analysis, Banks et al. (2016) sought to examine the redundancy between Authentic Leadership (AL) and Transformational Leadership (TL). This extensive study utilized a substantial sample size and drew from numerous sources. The findings indicated a strong positive true-score correlation between AL and follower's Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). The specific metrics of this correlation were noteworthy ($k = 10$, $N = 2.309$, $\rho = .48$), underscoring the close relationship between AL and OCB.

A notable meta-analysis by Hoch et al. (2018) examined the predictive power of Authentic Leadership (AL) on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). Utilizing the methodologies of J. E. Hunter and Schmidt (1990) through the Mark XIII meta-analysis program, the study yielded compelling results. The findings clearly demonstrated that authentic leadership serves as a significant predictor of overall organizational citizenship behavior. The statistical analysis provided robust evidence for this relationship, with $k = 8$, $N = 1.256$, $\rho = .33$, and $p < .001$.

The literature reviews presented below comprise distinct studies that analyze the correlations among independent, dependent, and control

variables. Each study contributes to a nuanced understanding of these relationships within the specified research context.

Quraishi and Aziz (2018) conducted a study to investigate the relationship between Authentic Leadership (AL) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) within educational settings, particularly in secondary schools. The research involved a survey of 500 educators and 32 school heads from 32 randomly selected schools. Data collection utilized two 16-item questionnaires: *Authentic Leadership Questionnaire* developed by Walumbwa (2008) and the Organizational Citizenship Behaviors Scale created by Smith et al. (1983). The findings revealed a weak yet positive correlation between certain dimensions of OCB and AL. Specifically, weak positive correlations were identified between relational transparency and OCB ($r = .09$, $p < .05$), internalized moral perspective and altruism ($r = .08$, $p = .05$), balanced processing and altruism ($r = .08$, $p = .05$), as well as between authentic leadership and altruism ($r = .08$, $p = .05$). However, it found no direct significant correlation between the overall construct of authentic leadership and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), with a correlation coefficient of $r = .08$.

In 2016, Yeşilkaya and Adin surveyed 400 public employees in Turkey to investigate the relationship between authentic leadership (AL) and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) from the employees' perspective. They employed the *Authentic Leadership Behavior Checklist* (Dalal, 2005; Spector et al., 2010). The study found a positive correlation between AL and OCB, with a coefficient of $\rho(\text{rho}) = .40$. This findings suggest that an increase in employees' perception of authentic leadership is related to an enhancement in their organizational citizenship behavior, reinforcing the strong relationship between the perception of AL and the enactment of OCB.

In 2011, Bakhshi et al. conducted a study with 77 National Hydroelectric Power Corporation Ltd participants in India. The primary objective of this research was to explore whether organizational commitment could serve as a predictor of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and to assess the potential of demographic variables on OCB. The researchers employed hierarchical regression analysis as their primary methodological approach to achieve this. Data collection was facilitated using the revised version of the *Organizational Citizenship Behavior Scale*, initially developed by Bakhshi and Kumar in 2009. This was specifically chosen to gauge the level of OCB among participants accurately within their organizational context. The study's findings provided valuable insights, particularly regarding the role of age in OCB. The hierarchical regression model indicated that age did not significantly affect the overall measure of OCB among participants. This outcome enhances the broader understanding of the factors influencing OCB in organizational settings, suggesting that age may not be a critical determinant in predicting the level of organizational citizenship behavior.

Abdullah and Kamil (2020) conducted a study involving 615 employees from a government institution in Putrajaya, Malaysia, to investigate the impact of demographic factors on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). They utilized a 16-item scale developed by Lee and Allen (2002) to measure OCB. The researchers applied various statistical methods for data analysis, including the Kruskal-Willis test, the Mann-Whitney U test, and the Bonferroni correction. The majority of participants were over the age of 30. The study revealed no significant differences in OCB scores across diverse age groups ($\chi^2(3) = 1.47$, $p = .69$)

Oladipupo's 2016 study examined the influence of perceived professional stress on the organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) of 300 randomly selected bankers from 12 banks in Ikeja, Lagos State, Nigeria. Employing the *Organizational Citizenship Behavior Checklist* (OCB-C) developed by Fox et al. (2012), the study's participant demographic consisted of 45% men and 55% women. The results of a *t*-test analysis revealed no significant difference in OCB levels between males and females bank employees.

In 2020, Abdullah and Kamil conducted a study to investigate the influence various demographic factors—such as gender, age, education, job position, and length of service—on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). The research involved 615 employees from a government institution in Putrajaya, Malaysia, utilizing Lee and Allen's 16-item *Organizational Citizenship Behavior Scale*. The sample consisted of 39.0% men and 60.0% women. The study revealed no significant differences in OCB scores between male and female participants through the application of statistical methods, including Kruskal-Wallis, Mann-Whitney U, and Bonferroni correction.

In 2011, Bakhshi et al. conducted a study examining the relationship between organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), focusing on the influence of various demographic variables. The research involved 77 participants, all National Hydroelectric Power Corporation Ltd employees in India, providing a diverse perspective on the organizational dynamics at play. The study employed the revised version of the *Organizational Citizenship Behavior Scale*, an instrument developed by Bakhshi and Kumar in 2009, to accurately assess the OCB level among the participants. The primary objective was to determine how demographic factors, such as age, gender, tenure, and marital status, could predict variations on OCB. Results were derived from a hierarchical regression model that specifically examined the role of tenure in influencing OCB. Surprisingly, the study revealed that tenure did not significantly impact the overall measure of OCB among the employees. This findings offers a unique insight into the determinants of organizational citizenship behavior, especially within the context of a prominent Indian corporation.

In 2012, Çavuş conducted a study involving 185 teachers from 27 public primary and secondary schools in Turkey to explore the relationship between workers' socialization levels and their Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). The participants included 70 females and 115 males teachers. To evaluate this relationship, Çavuş employed self-report survey in conjunction with the OCB scale developed by DiPaola. Additionally, the study examined the impact of demographic variables, such as tenure, on OCB. The research methodology used Pearson correlation and multiple regression analyses to assess the collected data thoroughly. The findings of this study were significant in enhancing the understanding of how socialization and demographic factors influence OCB. However, the statistical analysis revealed no significant correlation between tenure and OCB among the teachers involved. This outcome suggest that the duration of time teachers spent in their roles did not have a notable effect on their level of organizational citizenship behavior, according to the measure utilized in this study.

In 2014, Uzonwanne conducted a study examining the relationship between organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and various demographic factors among oil workers in Nigeria. The research utilized the *Organizational Citizenship Behavior Checklist* (OCB-C) questionnaire

developed by Fox and Spector (2009) to survey 300 oil workers with a range of educational backgrounds: 24 individual held master's degrees, 220 had bachelor's degrees or higher National Diplomas. A one-way ANOVA was employed to assess the impact of education level on OCB. The findings indicated no significant differences in OCB based on educational qualifications. This suggest that, within this context, a worker's level of education does not significantly influence their tendency to engage in organizational citizenship behavior. The study contributes to the understanding that factors beyond educational attainment may play a more pivotal role in shaping OCB among employees in the Nigerian oil sector.

In 2015, Berbaoui et al. conducted a research study at the National Company for Electricity and Gas Distribution in Bechar, Algeria, to explore the relationship between demographic characteristics and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). The study analyzed a sample of 126 employees, whose educational qualifications varied: 26.1% held diplomas, 47.6% had bachelor's degrees, and 4.76% had completed graduate studies. The researchers utilized Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), using marital status as the independent variable and OCB as the dependent variable. The ANOVA results indicated a non-significant main effect, demonstrating that education level did not substantially affect OCB. This suggests that employees' educational background did not meaningful impact their engagement in organizational citizenship behaviors within this specific organizational context. The findings underscore the complex nature of OCB and implies that factors beyond educational attainment may play a more significant role in shaping employees' citizenship behaviors in the workplace.

In 2017 study conducted by Saleem et al., the researcher aimed to investigate the relationship between psychological empowerment, various demographic factors, and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) among teachers. The study comprised a sample of 180 teachers from both private and public universities in Punjab. To collect data, the researcher utilized the *Organizational Citizenship Behavior Scale* developed by Podsakoff in 2000. They employed analytical methods such as ANOVA and independent *t*-test to explore the impact of demographic factors on OCB. One of the key demographic characteristics examined was marital status. The analysis indicated that marital status did not have a significant effect on OCB. Interestingly, the findings revealed no notable differences in the OCB levels between married and unmarried teachers, suggesting that marital status does not substantially influence teachers' engagement in organizational citizenship behaviors.

In 2013, Mahnaz et al. conducted a survey involving 333 staff members from various hospitals in Tehran to examine the relationship between demographic factors and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). They employed a multistage sampling technique to obtain a representative sample of hospital personnel. To analyze the data, the researchers utilized statistical tools such as one-way ANOVA and the Kruskal-Wallis Test. Their primary objective was to determine whether a significant correlation existed between ethnicity and OCB among the hospital staff. The analysis indicated no significant correlation between ethnicity and organizational citizenship behavior. This conclusion was supported by statistical findings, which revealed an alpha value of 0.083 and a *p*-value of less than 0.05. The absence of a significant correlation suggest that, within the context of these Tehran hospitals, ethnicity did

not substantially influence the levels or nature of organizational citizenship behavior demonstrated by the staff.

Methods

The participants in the study were recruited by using a snowball sampling technique, utilizing the researcher’s professional and personal networks. Through the use of a referral chain, the original participants were able to distribute and refer additional participants. The primary sources for recruitment for this investigation was through friends, coworkers, and contacts on social media platforms, specifically targeting educators and firefighters. The study sought to reach at least 2,500 people in the fire and education sectors, with the goal of obtaining involvement from 1,000 respondents. This goal was established to facilitate a significant snowball effect during the sampling procedure. The expected response rate was set at 10%, translating to roughly 250 participants. An online survey link was distributed to participants which included a demographic questionnaire, the *Authentic Leadership Questionnaire* (ALQ) and the *Organizational Citizenship Behavioral Checklist* (OCB-C). Participants must be at least eighteen years old to be eligible for the study. Teachers and Firefighters who are currently employed directly under the supervision of their superiors made up the focus group. At the start of the survey, a consent form requesting for the participant’s permission to participate in the study was displayed. This study utilized data collected from 289 participants who completed *Authentic Leadership Questionnaire* (ALQ) and the *Organizational Citizenship Behavioral Checklist* (OCB-C). Participants also reported their age, gender, education, tenure, marital status, occupation, and ethnicity.

The *Authentic Leadership Questionnaire* (ALQ) was administered to measure the levels of Relational Transparency, Internalized Moral Perspective, Balanced Processing, and Self-Awareness in the respondent. The ALQ is an inventory that analyzes behavioral aspects in leaders and consists of 16 items. The *Organizational Citizenship Behavioral Checklist* (OCB-C) was administered to participants to analyze organizational behavior towards people and their organization and consists of 12 items. This inventory evaluates followers’ contributions and interactions at the interpersonal level and organizational level and is essential for assessing followers’ self-rated organizational citizenship behavior.

SPSS version 26 was used to import all the data gathered for this study. A multiple regression analysis was used to determine if the independent variables: Relational Transparency, Internalized Moral Perspective, Balanced Processing, and Self-Awareness predicted Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB-O and OCB-P), beyond the impact of the control variables.

Null Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no relationship between Authentic Leadership (Self-Awareness, Relational Transparency, Balanced Processing, and Internalized Moral Perspective) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior- Organization (Sportsmanship, Conscientiousness, and Civic Virtue) as perceived by the follower when controlling for Age, Gender, Education, Tenure, Marital Status, Occupation, and Ethnicity.

H₀2: There is no relationship between Authentic Leadership (Self-Awareness, Relational Transparency, Balanced Processing, and Internal-

ized Moral Perspective) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior- People (Altruism and Courtesy) as perceived by the follower when controlling for Age, Gender, Education, Tenure, Marital Status, Occupation, and Ethnicity.

Results

Table 1 presents the Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient, a statistical measure employed to evaluate the internal consistency of the *Authentic Leadership Questionnaire* (ALQ). This metric is instrumental in determining the instrument’s reliability, indicating the extent to which items within the questionnaire correlate with one another. Furthermore, the table exhibited significant reliability across all sub-scales of Authentic Leadership, suggesting a robust alignment with the theoretical constructs associated with this leadership paradigm.

3.1 Table 1 Authentic Leadership Questionnaire Reliability

Authentic Leadership	ALQ	Martinez, 2024
Relational Transparency	.87	.89
Internalized Moral Perspective	.76	.93
Balanced Processing	.81	.89
Self-Awareness	.92	.95

Table 2 exhibited the Cronbach Alpha, a statistical measure employed to evaluate the internal consistency of the *Organizational Citizenship Behavior Checklist* (OCB-C). This metric is instrumental in determining the instrument’s reliability, indicating the extent to which items within the questionnaire correlate with one another. Moreover, the table exhibited significant reliability across both OCB dimensions, suggesting a robust alignment with the theoretical constructs associated with this behavior paradigm.

3.2 Table 2 Organizational Citizenship Behavior Checklist Reliability

OCB- Dimensions	OCB-C	Martinez, 2024
OCB-P	.75	.80
OCB-O	.82	.80

The results were illustrated through the Pearson Bivariate Correlation. This analysis explored the relationship between Authentic Leadership (independent variable) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (dependent variable). As presented in Table 3, the correlation coefficient range from -1 to +1, indicating varying strengths of association: coefficients from .01 to .29 represent weak relationships and .50 to 1 signify strong relationships.

Key findings from Table 3 reveal a positive correlation between tenure and Organizational Citizenship Behavior towards the organization (OCB-O), demonstrated by a coefficient of .607. Additionally

3.3 Table 3 Correlation Matrix of Continuous Variables

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Age (1)	1							
Tenure (2)	.067**	1						
Organizational Citizenship Behaviors – Organization (3)			1					
Organizational Citizenship Behaviors – People (4)	-.176**		.752**	1				
Transparency (5)	-.144*	-.171**	.272**	.212**	1			
Internalized Moral Perspective (6)	-.150*	-.130**	.272**	.215**	.870**	1		
Balanced Processing (7)	-.179**		.292**	.204**	.838**	.879**	1	
Self-Awareness (8)		-.137*	.296**	.230**	.840**	.838**	.895**	1

Note. * Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 ** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

This summary presents the results in Table 4, highlighting that OCB-O has two predictors. The first predictor, Occupation, indicated that firefighters outperformed teachers regarding OCB-O scores. Additionally, self-awareness demonstrated a significant positive relationship with OCB-O. Regarding OCB-P, self-awareness emerged as the sole significant predictor, showing a notable positive correlation with OCB-P.

3.4 Table 4 Summary of Results

Independent Variable	Dimension of Organizational Citizenship Behavior OCB-O	OCB-P
Age		
Gender		
Education		
Tenure		
Marital Status		
Occupation	(R ² = .037, p < .05) Firefighters > Teachers	
Ethnicity		
Relational Transparency		
Internalized Moral Perspective		
Balanced Processing		
Self-Awareness	(ΔR ² = .069, β = .269, r _a = .268, p < .05)	(R ² = .053, β = .230, p < .05)

Summary

This research investigated the relationship between authentic leadership and organizational citizenship behavior among firefighters and teachers while controlling for age, gender, education, tenure, marital status, occupation, and ethnicity. As an independent variable, authentic leadership comprises of four key dimensions: self-awareness, relational transparency, moral/ethics, and balanced processing. The Authentic Leadership Questionnaire (ALQ), developed by Walumbwa et al. (2008), was utilized to measure authentic leadership. In contrast, the Organizational Citizenship Behavior Checklist (OCB-C), created by Fox and Spector (2009), was created to assess the two components of organizational citizenship behavior: organizational citizenship behavior toward the organization and organization citizenship toward individuals.

The literature review indicated a limited number of studies examining the relationship between authentic leadership and the organizational citizenship behavior of firefighters and teachers. However, the findings from these studies have been inconsistent, with most reporting a positive correlation between the two variables. Furthermore, the literature review presented mixed results concerning demographic control variables and organizational citizenship behavior, showing both positive and negative

correlations, as well as nonsignificant findings. Notably, this study found a positive correlation between self-awareness and organizational citizenship behavior, particularly concerning both individual and organizational aspects. Additionally, the study revealed that occupation was correlated with organizational citizenship behavior towards the organization.

Limitations

The study's nonexperimental design restricts its generalizability to a larger population. The use of the snowball sampling method has drawbacks even if it may be useful for participant recruitment. Since the sample is based on a referral chain it can create a bias of only referring individuals who encompass traits being observed in the study which may lead to inadequate representation in the study. Furthermore, this study did not use random sampling and statistical tests that analyze random sampling could not be conducted for this study. Lastly, the study used self-reported data, which is prone to biases and inaccuracies.

It is important to note that highly correlated variables in a study may have an impact on the findings. For example, there was a high degree of intercorrelation between Authentic Leadership facets and the dimensions of Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Determining the distinct contributions of each variable to the outcome under investigation may become difficult as a result and may lead to multicollinearity making it more difficult to interpret regression coefficients. However, it is crucial to realize that strong intercorrelations don't always mean that a study's conclusions are invalid.

Recommendations for Future Research

Several recommendations should be considered to enhance the quality of future research. One significant challenge encountered during the survey distribution to teachers and firefighters was the reliance on personal and professional networks. While these networks can provide valuable participant sources, they may also lead to a limited sample size or biased selection. Therefore, to broaden the scope of the study and obtain a more representative sample, future researchers should seek authorization from local governments and schools districts. These entities can facilitate access to a more extensive and diverse pool of potential participants, encompassing a range of backgrounds, experiences, and perspectives. Similarly, expanding the study population to include all public service employees could significantly boost response rates and sample size in future research efforts. To deepen our understanding of the impact of leadership on behavior—particularly regarding Organizational Citizenship Behavior—it would be advantageous for future researchers to replicate this study using various leadership styles, such as servant leadership. This focus is particularly pertinent since firefighters and teachers are recognized as public servants.

Moreover, exploring the Full-Range Leadership Model could yield insights into how different leadership dimensions affect employees behavior. Future researchers should also incorporate additional variables, such as income, personality traits, work environment, and stress levels to

evaluate their potential influence on the study's outcomes. This comprehensive approach could provide a clearer understanding of the underlying mechanisms involved, thereby enhancing the accuracy and validity of the findings.

Implications and Key Take Aways

This study revealed that leaders possessing a higher degree of self-awareness tend to positively influence their followers to engage in greater organizational citizenship behaviors towards their colleagues. This suggests that leaders who deeply understand their own personal qualities may encourage their team members to transcend their job responsibilities and willingly support one another. According to Krishnan and Arora (2008), leaders who demonstrate strong interpersonal skills and maintain a composed demeanor are more effective in fostering organizational citizenship behavior among their team members. Additionally, Kernodle et al. (2003) indicate that promoting Organizational Citizenship Behaviors (OCBs) among employees can enhance their job performance, improve group effectiveness, and contribute to the organization's overall success. Consequently, managers who inspire such behavior in their employees play a vital role in the success of their organization.

Moreover, leaders possessing high levels of self-awareness can significantly influence their subordinates to engage in more Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) towards the organization. This suggests that a leader's understanding of their own personality traits may inspire employees to voluntarily go beyond their job responsibilities and work diligently towards the organization's success. Krishnan and Arora (2008) assert that a leader's ability to connect with team members is essential for fostering, encouraging, and motivating OCB among staff.

In addition, this research indicates that firefighters exhibit higher levels of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) than teachers. These findings suggest that firefighters are more inclined to engage in actions that benefit their organizations, including going above and beyond their primary responsibilities, assisting colleagues and the community, and enhancing overall performance for the organization's greater good. As outlined by Rayner et al. (2012), employees demonstrate Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) by exerting voluntary efforts that exceed the expectations of their formal employment contracts to promote the organization's interests. Since these actions add value to the organization, leaders and companies have valid concerns. Any reduction in such behavior will likely affect the organization's overall performance (Rayner et al., 2012).

Key Takeaways

- Leaders should attend workshops that can improve their self-awareness
- Organizations should provide self-evaluations to help emphasize the value of self-awareness
- Personality assessments, feedback surveys, and self-reflection exercises are recommended to help foster self-awareness in leadership roles

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